

Students' challenges and needs in essay writing: A qualitative study at Universitas Syiah Kuala

Dian FAJRINA, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia ¹

Andri WARDANA, Mae Fah Luang University, Thailand

Tsair Ahmad Jibril ASKARI, Universitas Syiah Kuala

Essay writing is a fundamental component of academic literacy in English Education programs. Many EFL students continue to face difficulties despite completing essay writing courses. This qualitative descriptive study aims to identify students' linguistic difficulties in essay writing and explore their learning needs after completing the course. The study was conducted at the Department of English Education, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia. Data were collected through a closed-ended questionnaire administered to 93 fifth-semester students and semi-structured interviews with 10 selected participants. The findings reveal that grammar is perceived as the most severe difficulty ($M = 4.17$), while word choice is the most frequently reported issue (61.83%) with lower intensity ($M = 3.75$). Other aspects, including organization, supporting ideas, and spelling, are moderate difficulties whereas punctuation and capitalization are less problematic. The findings reveal the need for clearer instruction, ongoing feedback, and sustained support in essay-writing classes.

Keywords: EFL Students; Essay Writing; Learning Needs; Linguistics Difficulties

1. Introduction

To achieve communicative competence in English, learners must acquire proficiency in four interrelated skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Each of these skills plays a critical role in language acquisition. Listening and reading enable learners to receive and interpret language, understand context, and respond appropriately, while speaking and writing allow them to produce language to express thoughts, engage in communication, and construct meaning (Hinkel, 2012).

Writing is one of the four essential language skills and plays a particularly important role in academic contexts (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007, 2016).

¹ Corresponding Author: dian_fajrina@usk.ac.id

Although it is often considered the most challenging skill, writing is central to language learning because it helps consolidate grammar, vocabulary, and critical thinking (Songjin et al., 2023). It also serves not only as a means of communication but as a tool for learning and academic success (Salmani Nodoushan, 2023). According to Graham et al. (2019), writing enables learners to express ideas, reflect on experiences, persuade audiences, and engage with knowledge across disciplines. Its complexity arises from the need for linguistic accuracy, organizational coherence, and cognitive planning (Jaya, 2025).

In higher education, particularly within English Education programs, essay writing is essential for developing academic literacy, engaging in scholarly discourse, and preparing students for their future roles as educators. Essay writing is not only an academic requirement but also a practical skill that enables future educators to analyze and design instructional content (Amo Sánchez-Fortún et al., 2024). However, many EFL students still struggle with essay writing (Asnas & Hidayanti, 2024; Fadhly et al, 2026). These difficulties often stem from linguistic issues, such as grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure, as well as cognitive and psychological factors, including low confidence, limited idea generation, and ineffective writing strategies (Salmani Nodoushan, 2018).

Previous studies have consistently stressed the complex challenges inherent in EFL writing, ranging from foundational mechanics to complex cognitive processes. At the structural and linguistic level, Ariyanti and Fitriana (2017) observed that Indonesian English majors struggle significantly with grammatical accuracy, cohesion, and coherence, often exacerbated by limited vocabulary and poor paragraph organization. These findings are further categorized by Salmani Nodoushan (2018), who analyzed a vast 20-year corpus to conclude that EFL writing errors are most effectively classified into three primary dimensions: structural, discursive, and cognitive. Even among high-achieving students in Banda Aceh, Yusuf et al. (2021) discovered that grammatical inaccuracies, specifically of the omission type, remain prevalent, primarily due to intralanguage factors rather than native language interference.

Building on these linguistic concerns, several researchers have pinpointed specific mechanical and technical barriers that diminish writing quality. Purnama (2021) identified limitations in word formation, punctuation, and tense usage as major obstacles, while Tambunan et al. (2022) reported that persistent issues with grammar and writing mechanics negatively impact overall clarity. In the same vein, Asnas and Hidayanti (2024) confirmed that these foundational difficulties in grammar, vocabulary, and organization remain pervasive across the EFL contexts.

Beyond surface-level errors, recent research has shifted focus toward the strategic and procedural difficulties students face during the writing process. Bisriyah (2022) revealed that the most significant hurdles often occur during the initial stages of outlining and idea generation, which subsequently compromise the drafting and revising phases. While the need for step-by-step instruction is urgent, Ariyanti and Fitriana (2017) noted that such pedagogical support is frequently hindered by the practical constraints of large class sizes and limited instructional time.

In terms of learning needs, a review by Al-Jarf (2026), which analyzed 20 studies, highlighted that students benefit most from process-oriented and learner-centered instruction. The review emphasized the importance of meaningful writing tasks, support in generating ideas, and selective, focused feedback rather than comprehensive error correction. This suggested that effective writing instruction should prioritize guided practice and strategic feedback to help students gradually develop their writing competence.

While previous research established that EFL writing difficulties encompass both linguistic and strategic hurdles, a significant gap exists in understanding the specific learning needs required to address these challenges within localized institutional contexts.

Preliminary findings at Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia, corroborate this, revealing that even after completing formal coursework, students face persistent barriers in grammatical accuracy, vocabulary, and writing mechanics, such as punctuation and capitalization. Consequently, this study investigates these observable linguistic difficulties, specifically grammar, vocabulary, organization, and mechanics, together with students' corresponding learning needs. By prioritizing a comprehensive analysis of writing performance over psychological factors, this research aims to provide a contextualized framework for the precise instructional support necessary to meet academic essay writing demands.

Based on these issues, the study addresses the following research questions:

- (1) What linguistic difficulties do students who have completed the Essay Writing Course have?
- (2) What specific learning needs do these students have to improve their essay writing performance?

By analyzing students' difficulties and learning needs, this study is expected to contribute to the field of English language teaching, particularly in academic writing and students' linguistic development.

2. Background

Writing is widely acknowledged as the process of transforming thoughts, feelings, and ideas into written form. According to Lindsay (2020), writing is a cognitive process in which authors generate texts based on their ideas through a series of mental activities. In this sense, writing can also be understood as a structured form of communication that serves various purposes and styles.

Writing can be understood as the process of producing meaningful text by organizing ideas through appropriate structures, vocabulary, and grammar. It is not merely a transcription of spoken language, but a complex cognitive activity that involves planning, drafting, and revising (Flower & Hayes, 1981; Nunan, 2003). Similarly, Graham et al. (2019) emphasized that writing is a fundamental academic skill that enables students to express ideas, evaluate information, and construct meaning across disciplines. Writing demands a high level of cognitive involvement, including the organization of ideas and the effective use of language features such as vocabulary, syntax, and structure. As widely recognized, it is an essential tool for clear communication, academic success, and self-expression in both educational and professional contexts.

In EFL settings, essay writing plays a particularly important role as both an academic requirement and a means of developing critical thinking. Safitri and Adani (2024) found that essay writing encourages students' ability to interpret, analyze, and synthesize ideas effectively. Similarly, Hamamah et al. (2022) argued that academic writing, especially essays, inherently requires critical thinking through processes such as interpretation, analysis, and evaluation. The ability to write essays is, therefore, a key competency in academic writing. However, mastering this skill remains challenging. Ulugbek and Anora (2020) noted that essay writing is one of the more difficult forms of writing. In EFL contexts, particularly in Indonesia, essay writing tasks are widely used to assess both language proficiency and subject knowledge (Putri & Cahyono, 2020).

In this connection, linguistic difficulties in essay writing cover several challenges related to a student's mastery of language components, specifically mechanics, grammar, vocabulary, and organization. These barriers often hinder the production of clear, accurate, and well-structured academic prose. A qualitative study by Riadil et al. (2023) identified grammar as the most pervasive difficulty among EFL learners, followed by vocabulary and organizational issues, while emphasizing that even mechanical problems like punctuation significantly disrupt coherence.

At the mechanical level, errors in spelling, capitalization, and punctuation serve as initial barriers to readability. Muhassin et al. (2020) explained that spelling difficulties frequently arise from the inconsistency between English phonology

and orthography, which reduces the credibility of academic work. In the Indonesian context, Siregar et al. (2023) and Habibi et al. (2017) reported that spelling errors often lead to the misinterpretation of meaning and are typically linked to limited lexical familiarity. Similarly, capitalization remains a persistent issue; Asnas and Hidayanti (2024) highlighted that students often apply rules inconsistently despite possessing foundational knowledge. Furthermore, Nugraha and Fiftinova (2026) and Ariyanti and Fitriana (2017) observed that confusion over commas, full stops, and apostrophes creates unclear sentence boundaries and disrupts the flow of ideas, effectively reducing the formality of the writing.

Beyond mechanics, grammatical and lexical precision are essential for academic clarity. Habibi et al. (2017) and Ariyanti and Fitriana (2017) consistently found that errors in tense usage, subject-verb agreement, and sentence construction obscure meaning and reduce overall quality. These findings are reinforced by Normawati and Nugrahaeni (2024), who identified article usage and tense consistency as primary sources of frustration for learners. Parallel to these grammatical hurdles is the challenge of vocabulary. Habibi et al. (2017) emphasized that word choice is a dominant issue; limited lexical knowledge leads to vague expressions and a lack of confidence in selecting precise academic language, preventing students from expressing complex ideas effectively.

Finally, the most complex linguistic difficulties manifest at the organizational and developmental levels. The structural integrity of an essay is often compromised in the pre-writing phase; Bisriyah (2022) indicated that many students bypass essential outlining and planning stages, leading to illogical sequencing and a fragmented narrative. Fareed et al. (2016) further noted that a lack of understanding of rhetorical patterns results in unclear transitions between the introduction, body, and conclusion. This organizational weakness is often coupled with a failure to develop supporting ideas. Riswanto (2021) and Ariyanti and Fitriana (2017) argued that while students may produce topic sentences, they frequently fail to provide the logical explanations, examples, or depth required to establish a persuasive academic argument, eventually writing incoherent and surface-level essays.

These point to students' needs in learning how to write essays. Students' learning needs in essay writing are grounded in the concept of needs analysis proposed by Hutchinson and Waters (1987), who define learning needs as what learners need to do to learn effectively. This concept includes not only linguistic skills but also learning processes, resources, and environmental factors that support students in achieving their goals. In the context of writing instruction, learning needs encompass learners' purposes, strategies, materials, and the support they receive throughout the writing process.

Building on this theoretical foundation, Taufiq et al. (2021) developed a practical framework to analyze students' learning needs in a university-level Essay Writing Course. Their framework consists of five key indicators: (1) the purpose of learning essay writing, (2) learning methods, (3) available learning resources, (4) students' characteristics, and (5) course setting. These indicators were derived from Hutchinson and Waters' (1987) theory and were used to design both questionnaires and interview instruments in their study.

Based on these findings, the present study synthesizes and expands these indicators into nine interrelated dimensions to construct a more systematic and operational framework. These dimensions include (1) the purpose of learning, (2) learning methods, (3) learning resources, (4) students' characteristics, (5) course setting, (6) motivating strategies, (7) opportunities for practice, (8) guidance for revision, and (9) learner autonomy. This framework represents the operationalization of Hutchinson and Waters' (1987) needs analysis theory within the context of essay writing. It also serves as the basis for developing interview guidelines and analyzing qualitative data in this study.

Taken together, the findings of Taufiq et al. (2021) suggested that students' learning needs extend beyond linguistic challenges to include instructional, material, and environmental support. These aspects play a crucial role in shaping effective writing instruction and student engagement. Therefore, the nine-dimensional framework adopted in this study provides a comprehensive foundation for examining and addressing students' learning needs in essay writing.

3. Method

3.1. Design

This study employed a qualitative descriptive approach to explore the difficulties and learning needs of students who had completed the Essay Writing Course in the Department of English Education, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia. This approach was considered appropriate because it enables an in-depth exploration of participants' experiences, perceptions, and expressed needs (Creswell & Poth, 2016), particularly as essay writing involves cognitive, linguistic, and affective processes (Ary et al., 2018). By focusing on students' subjective experiences, this study aims to identify both the difficulties they encounter and their views on effective pedagogical support.

3.2. Participants

The participants of this study were 93 undergraduate students from the Department of English Education, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia, who had

completed the Essay Writing Course with a minimum grade of C. Students with borderline grades (C or equivalent) were considered particularly relevant as they were more likely to experience writing difficulties. In addition, 10 students were selected for in-depth interviews based on their questionnaire responses using purposive sampling, as they were actively engaged in essay writing activities.

3.3. Instruments

The questionnaire used in this study is a closed-ended instrument adopted from Habibi et al. (2017), designed to identify specific linguistic problems students face in essay writing. It consists of 28 statements covering key aspects of writing. Each statement was rated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." This format allows for the quantification of students' self-perceived difficulties while ensuring clarity and consistency in data interpretation.

In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted to obtain more in-depth information about students' learning needs in essay writing. The interview guideline was adapted from the framework proposed by Hutchinson and Waters (1987) on learning needs. In line with this framework, the interview protocol was further developed based on the findings of Taufiq et al. (2021). The semi-structured format also enabled the researcher to use follow-up questions (or probes) when necessary to clarify or deepen participants' responses.

3.4. Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed online using Google Forms. Data collection through this instrument aimed to systematically identify common linguistic problems students face in essay writing. The questionnaire also collected demographic data, including gender, current semester, and essay writing grade, to characterize participants and identify those representing different levels of writing achievement.

After reviewing the questionnaire responses, 10 students were selected for interviews using purposive sampling. The interviews were conducted individually, either face-to-face or through online video calls, depending on participant availability. Each session lasted approximately 15-20 minutes and was audio-recorded with participants' consent.

The responses obtained from the closed-ended questionnaire were first downloaded from Google Forms as a spreadsheet. The quantitative data from the Likert-scale questionnaire were analyzed by calculating mean scores to determine the intensity of perceived difficulties. To interpret the mean scores,

this study adopted the classification proposed by Habibi et al. (2017), which categorizes scores into five levels: 1.00-1.80 (Very Low), 1.81-2.60 (Low), 2.61-3.40 (Medium), 3.41-4.20 (High), and 4.21-5.00 (Very High). This categorization was used to assess the level of students' perceived difficulties across writing aspects.

The qualitative interview data were analyzed using the interactive model proposed by Miles et al. (2020), which involved the three concurrent flows of data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. During these stages, the researchers transcribed the audio recordings, coded key statements into themes such as linguistic difficulties and learning needs, and organized these themes into summaries. Finally, the findings were compared with questionnaire results through triangulation to ensure data validity and provide a comprehensive understanding of the students' experiences.

4. Results

This section presents the findings of the study concerning (1) students' linguistic difficulties and (2) learning needs in essay writing.

4.1. Students' linguistic difficulties in essay writing

The overall results of students' difficulties in essay writing are presented in Table 1. The findings indicate that grammar has the highest level of intensity, while word choice is the most widely reported difficulty based on percentage, followed by organization, which is categorized as a medium-level difficulty. Meanwhile, supporting ideas and spelling are also categorized as moderate difficulties whereas capitalization and punctuation are perceived as low-level difficulties.

Table 1
Overall Students' Difficulties in Essay Writing

No	Aspect	Mean	Percentage (A+SA)	Level
1	Grammar	4.17	47.04%	High
2	Word Choice	3.75	61.83%	High
3	Organization	3.37	49.19%	Medium
4	Supporting Ideas	3.03	31.45%	Medium
5	Spelling	3.00	34.68%	Medium
6	Capitalization	2.29	25.54%	Low
7	Punctuation	2.09	12.90%	Low

Data reported in Table 1 indicate that grammar is perceived as the most serious linguistic difficulty in essay writing. The overall mean score for grammatical difficulties is 4.17, which falls into the 'High' category, indicating

strong agreement among the students regarding grammatical problems. Although the percentage of students affected by grammar problems (47.04%) is not the highest, the high mean score suggests that those who experience grammatical difficulties face them intensely. See Appendix A for questionnaire items that measure this dimension of writing.

Word choice emerged as the second most serious difficulty and the most widespread problem among students. The overall mean score for word choice was 3.75, which is categorized as High, with 61.83% of students agreeing or strongly agreeing that they experienced difficulties in this aspect. The students reported a heavy reliance on simple vocabulary and a lack of confidence in using varied or academic words. These findings indicate that lexical limitations play a crucial role in shaping their difficulties in essay writing (See Appendix A).

Organizational difficulties were perceived at a Medium-High level, with an overall mean score of 3.37 and 49.19% agreement among students. These difficulties were mainly related to brainstorming ideas, developing outlines, and organizing ideas into a logical structure. The findings suggest that organizational skills remain a significant challenge in students' academic writing process (See Appendix A).

Difficulties in supporting ideas were categorized at a Medium level, with an overall mean score of 3.03 and 31.45% agreement among students. The students reported challenges in generating relevant supporting details, maintaining idea development, and locating appropriate sources. These findings indicate that their difficulties extend beyond linguistic accuracy to include challenges in elaborating and supporting ideas in academic essays (See Appendix A).

Spelling difficulties were categorized at a Medium level, with an overall mean score of 3.00. Approximately 34.68% of students agreed or strongly agreed that spelling was problematic in their essay writing. They commonly experienced difficulty spelling unfamiliar or newly learned words and reported that reviewing spelling errors required considerable time. Although spelling difficulties were not the most dominant issue, they still affected the accuracy and professionalism of students' essays (See Appendix A).

Capitalization difficulties obtained an overall mean score of 2.29, placing this aspect at a Low level. Only 25.54% of students reported experiencing significant capitalization problems. Most of them were aware of capitalization rules for personal names, while errors more frequently occurred at the beginning of sentences and in place names. Compared to other linguistic aspects, capitalization was perceived as a relatively minor difficulty (See Appendix A).

Punctuation was identified as the least problematic linguistic aspect. Punctuation difficulties obtained an overall mean score of 2.09, which is categorized as Low. Only 12.90% of students agreed or strongly agreed that punctuation posed serious problems. They mainly experienced confusion in distinguishing between commas and periods, using apostrophes, and choosing between commas and conjunctions. However, compared to other linguistic aspects, punctuation difficulties were relatively minor and did not significantly hinder their essay writing performance (See Appendix A).

4.2. Students' learning needs in essay writing

In this study, students' responses were grouped into nine themes to ensure consistency between the research instrument and the data analysis. This thematic organization enables the researcher to identify not only students' experiences in learning essay writing but also their needs in terms of instructional support, learning environment, and independent learning development.

The first interview question explored students' purposes for learning essay writing, both at present and in the future. The findings indicate that students learn essay writing for clear academic and professional reasons. Most of them viewed it as an essential skill for completing coursework, writing their thesis, pursuing further studies, and preparing for future careers. This suggests that their learning needs are strongly goal-oriented and closely linked to their long-term academic and professional development. The following responses show that they perceive essay writing as a foundational academic skill that directly affects their future opportunities.

- (1) Mastering essay writing is important for me to complete my courses, prepare for English proficiency tests, and support my academic goals. (P4)
- (2) Mastering essay writing is very important for me to continue my master's study and pursue a career as a lecturer. (P7)
- (3) Mastering essay writing is important for my academic graduation as well as for scholarship opportunities and future employment. (P8)

As for 'learning needs related to teaching method', the second interview question focused on the learning methods that students find most helpful in essay writing. The findings indicate that they prefer approaches emphasizing active practice, the use of model texts, and continuous feedback. Rather than relying on theory-based instruction, most of them expressed a need for hands-on activities that allow them to observe, practice, and revise their writing. This suggests that their learning needs are oriented toward a process-based

approach that integrates modeling, guided practice, and feedback to effectively develop their essay writing skills.

- (4) I benefit more from direct practice accompanied by examples and immediate feedback than from learning theory alone. (P6)
- (5) I apply an observe-imitate-modify approach by studying high-quality essays and then rewriting them using my own language. (P8)
- (6) I find it more helpful when the lecturer provides complete model essays accompanied by explanations of structure and feedback. (P3)

The third interview question explored the learning resources students need most for essay writing. The findings indicate that they rely on a range of resources, including grammar-checking applications, online dictionaries, books, and model essays from both online and printed sources. These resources help improve language accuracy, expand vocabulary, and enhance understanding of essay organization. This suggests that access to appropriate learning resources, both technological tools and written models, is an essential component of their learning needs and supports their independent writing development.

- (7) I use books, online dictionaries, and applications such as Grammarly as my learning resources. (P5)
- (8) I use grammar-checking applications and a thesaurus as my main learning resources. (P8)
- (9) I need online writing samples and writing guides as references. (P9)

The fourth interview question explored students' learning styles and personal learning characteristics. The findings indicate that they have diverse learning preferences that influence how they approach essay writing, with most participants favoring visual input and direct practice. They reported better understanding when provided with concrete examples, followed by opportunities to practice and receive clarification. This suggests that they require instructional approaches that actively engage them in the writing process and align with their preference for visual and practice-oriented learning.

- (10) My learning style is visual, so I need concrete examples. (P2)
- (11) I learn more effectively through direct practice that allows immediate questions and clarification. (P6)
- (12) My learning style is visual and is followed by practice. (P3)

The fifth interview question focused on the classroom setting that best supports students' active participation in essay writing. The findings indicate

that the learning environment plays a significant role in their writing development, with most of them preferring small and focused classes. Such settings allow greater interaction with lecturers and create a more comfortable atmosphere for asking questions and receiving feedback. A supportive and less crowded classroom was also perceived as helpful in reducing anxiety and increasing engagement. These findings suggest that students need a course setting that promotes close interaction, individual attention, and frequent practice.

- (13) I feel more comfortable learning in a small class because interaction with the lecturer is more intensive. (P4)
- (14) I feel more comfortable in a small and less crowded class so that I can focus better and reduce anxiety. (P7)
- (15) I feel more comfortable learning in a small class with many practice opportunities. (P10)

The sixth interview question examined the techniques and strategies that motivate students in learning essay writing. The findings indicate that their motivation is influenced by both external and internal factors, with external motivation stemming from lecturer feedback and academic demands, and internal motivation driven by personal goals and the desire for improvement. Students reported increased motivation when they received constructive feedback and observed progress in their writing. These results suggest that strategies such as continuous feedback, recognition of progress, and goal-oriented instruction are essential for supporting their learning.

- (16) I am motivated by my academic goals and by improvements in the quality of my writing based on lecturer feedback. (P5)
- (17) I am motivated by lecturer feedback and by my personal desire to be able to write and express ideas in English. (P9)
- (18) My motivation is related to my plan to continue my studies at the master's level. (P1)

The seventh interview question explored the amount and type of writing practice students need. The findings indicate that they require frequent opportunities to practice and actively participate in essay writing activities. Most of them emphasized that regular practice is essential for developing fluency, accuracy, and confidence. They preferred short but consistent practice sessions that allow them to apply what they have learned and receive feedback. These results suggest that their learning needs include regular and sustained opportunities for active participation in writing tasks.

- (19) I need to practice at least once a week and ideally every day. (P8)

- (20) I practice about two to three times a week. (P3)
- (21) I practice writing up to four to five times a week. (P4)
- (22) To master essay writing, I need to practice about five times a week. (P1)

The eighth interview question examined the type of guidance students need when revising their essays. The findings indicate that they require clear, detailed, and continuous guidance throughout the revision process. Most of them expected lecturers to provide specific feedback that not only identifies errors but also explains how to improve them. This type of guidance helps students better understand their weaknesses and make more effective revisions. These results suggest that revision support is a crucial component of their learning needs in essay writing.

- (23) I need lecturer feedback that is not only written but also accompanied by concrete examples. (P6)
- (24) I need specific feedback that directly addresses clarity, structure, and language quality. (P5)
- (25) I need written feedback that focuses on spelling errors. (P10)

The ninth interview question explored how lecturers or the course can support students in becoming more active and taking control of their learning. The findings indicate that students do not rely solely on lecturers but also take active roles in managing their own learning. Many students reported using tools and strategies such as grammar-checking applications, dictionaries, rubrics, and model essays to support independent learning. This suggests that they are developing learner autonomy and taking greater responsibility for improving their writing skills. These results highlight the need for support in fostering autonomy and self-regulated learning strategies.

- (26) My independence is supported by the use of dictionaries, grammar checkers, and assessment checklists or rubrics. (P8)
- (27) My independence is supported by the use of AI tools to find references and enrich my ideas. (P9)
- (28) My independence is supported by assessment checklists, step-by-step writing guides, and access to model essays. (P3)

5. Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that grammar remains the most formidable linguistic barrier for EFL students, even after the completion of formal essay-writing coursework. With a mean score of 4.17, grammatical difficulty is perceived with high intensity, particularly regarding tense usage and sentence construction. This outcome aligns with the observations of Ariyanti and

Fitriana (2017), who noted that Indonesian English majors struggle significantly with grammatical accuracy and sentence formation. Furthermore, the high intensity of these errors suggests that students face a heavy cognitive load when attempting to balance linguistic accuracy with the complex task of academic writing.

While grammar showed the highest intensity, word choice was the most widespread problem, affecting 61.83% of participants. Students reported a pervasive reliance on simple vocabulary and a marked lack of confidence in utilizing varied academic lexicon. These lexical limitations directly hinder their ability to express ideas with precision and clarity. Such findings corroborate the work of Habibi et al. (2017), which identified word choice as a dominant issue stemming from limited lexical knowledge. As writing serves as a tool for academic success and knowledge engagement, these vocabulary gaps represent a critical hurdle in achieving full academic literacy.

Structural and organizational challenges were also prominent, categorized as medium-level difficulties. Students specifically identified brainstorming and outlining as significant obstacles in their writing process. This lack of strategic preparation frequently results in illogical sequencing and underdeveloped paragraphs. These results are consistent with the findings of Bisriyah (2022), who argued that bypassing the planning stage leads to a “messy” writing process and incoherent narratives. Furthermore, the difficulty students faced in developing supporting ideas echoes the concerns of Purnawarman et al. (2016), who observed that while students can often state a topic, they struggle to provide relevant evidence or elaboration.

In contrast to structural issues, mechanical aspects such as spelling, capitalization, and punctuation were perceived as less problematic. Punctuation, in particular, received the lowest difficulty rating ($M = 2.09$). While Nugraha and Fiftinova (2026) have argued that punctuation misuse can obscure meaning, the participants in this localized context viewed it as a minor concern compared to grammar and organization. However, spelling and capitalization errors still occurred inconsistently, particularly at the beginning of sentences and with proper nouns. This inconsistency reflects the findings of Asnas and Hidayanti (2024), suggesting that students may possess foundational mechanical knowledge but fail to apply it reliably in high-stakes academic contexts.

Regarding learning needs, the data reveal a strong student preference for active, process-based pedagogy over theoretical instruction (see also Firoozjantigh et al., 2021). Participants emphasized the need for model texts, hands-on practice, and continuous, specific feedback that explains how to correct errors rather than just identifying them. This aligns with the review by Al-Jarf (2026), that found that students benefit most from learner-centered

instruction and focused feedback (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010; Wiboolyasarini & Jinowat, 2025). The call for clearer instruction and smaller class sizes further highlights the practical constraints, such as large classes and limited time, that previously hindered lecturers in Indonesian universities.

Finally, the study highlights the emergence of learner autonomy as a crucial component of student development. Participants reported significant reliance on independent resources, including online dictionaries, grammar-checking applications like Grammarly, and AI tools to manage their writing tasks. This shift toward self-regulated learning corresponds with the indicators of student characteristics and learner autonomy within the frameworks of Hutchinson and Waters (1987) and Taufiq et al. (2021). Ultimately, providing a scaffold that integrates these technological tools with guided pedagogical support appears essential for helping EFL students meet the rigorous demands of academic essay writing.

6. Conclusion

This study examined students' linguistic difficulties and learning needs in essay writing among fifth-semester students of the English Education Department at Universitas Syiah Kuala using questionnaires and interviews. The findings revealed that grammar and word choice were the most serious difficulties, indicating students' limited control of sentence structure and academic vocabulary. Difficulties in organization and supporting ideas further suggested that many students struggled to construct coherent academic arguments, while mechanical aspects such as spelling, punctuation, and capitalization continued to affect the overall quality of their writing. The interview results showed that these difficulties are closely linked to students' learning needs, as they viewed essay writing as essential for academic success and future careers. Consequently, students expressed strong needs for guided practice, model texts, continuous feedback, access to learning resources, and supportive classroom environments.

This study has several limitations. First, the questionnaire data were based on students' self-reported perceptions, which may not fully reflect their actual writing performance. Second, the interview involved only ten participants, limiting the generalizability of the qualitative findings. Third, the study focused primarily on linguistic difficulties and learning needs without examining psychological factors such as anxiety or motivation in depth. Future research is therefore recommended to include larger and more diverse samples, incorporate analysis of students' actual writing products, and explore additional factors such as affective variables, instructional strategies, or longitudinal development in essay writing skills to provide a more comprehensive understanding of students' writing development.

Authors' Statement

Dian Fajrina worked on data analysis and interpretation, and final editing of the manuscript. Tsair Ahmad Jibril Askari assisted in the data collection and manuscript drafting. Andri Wardana contributed to the verification of the results, discussion, and proofreading.

The Author(s)

Dian Fajrina (Email: dian_fajrina@usk.ac.id) is a lecturer at the Department of English Education, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia. She pursued her Doctoral degree from the University of Canterbury, New Zealand, focusing on the influence of the Indonesian culture on the Indonesian EFL students' writing. Her research interests are English language teaching, EFL writing, and Cross-cultural Understanding.

Tsair Ahmad Jibril Askari (Email: emailjibril@gmail.com) graduated from the English Education Department at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Universitas Syiah Kuala. Her research interests are English language teaching and language assessment.

Andri Wardana (Email: andri.war@mfu.ac.th) is currently a lecturer in the English Department, School of Liberal Arts, Mae Fah Luang University, Chiang Rai, Thailand. He obtained his Bachelor's degree in English Education from Universitas Syiah Kuala in 2016, followed by a Master's degree in TESOL from the University of New South Wales, Australia, in 2019. His research interests include Technology-enhanced Language Teaching and Learning, English for Specific Purposes, EFL Writing, and Automated Written Corrective Feedback.

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Appendix A: Questionnaire Items

No Grammatical Difficulties

- 1 A frequent problem is using the correct tenses
- 2 Having difficulties using passive voice in writing
- 3 Having poor grammar makes my writing not so good
- 4 Grammar makes me take a long time to put the correct tenses that are appropriate to the event

Punctuation Difficulties

- 5 Feeling confused about putting the correct punctuation
- 6 Getting confused to put between full stop and comma
- 7 Facing trouble in using apostrophes in contractions and possessives
- 8 Getting confused about whether to put a comma or a conjunction to continue to the next sentence

Word Choice Difficulties

- 9 Always use simple words in writing
- 10 Using simple words in writing makes me more confident
- 11 Lack of vocabulary makes me get confused when writing
- 12 Using new vocabularies take long time

Organization Difficulties

- 13 Getting difficulties in writing techniques (brainstorming)
- 14 Having poorly written material to organize can sometimes fail to select a topic
- 15 Outlining writing
- 16 Making mind mapping in writing

Spelling Difficulties

- 17 The spelling of a word is not important in writing
- 18 Having difficulties in checking the spelling of new words
- 19 Reviewing writing to check the spelling of the words
- 20 Checking the spelling of words takes a long time for me

Capitalization Difficulties

- 21 Capitalization is not important
- 22 Sometimes forget to put capitalization after a full stop
- 23 Getting confused about putting capitalization in the first letter of the name of a city
- 24 Capitalization is needed in the first letter of a person's name

Difficulties in Supporting Ideas

- 25 I face many troubles in constructing words to support the ideas
 - 26 I am difficult to define what is related to the topic
 - 27 Getting confused and having no idea of a supporting sentence
 - 28 I have difficulty finding the source. Not only from the internet but also from the book. I am too lazy to read some books. Because I should make a summary of the book that I have read. To make the idea coherent. It is very difficult.
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